

Determinants of Public Service Performance in the Manpower Social Security Organizing Agency (Case Study in Ternate City, Indonesia)

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ABSTRACT : At present the public does not like convoluted services caused by long bureaucratic chains. People want bureaucratic services that can understand their needs and wants fulfilled in a relatively short time. This study aims to determine the determinants of public service performance in the Social Security Organizing Agency (SSOA) of Ternate City. The method used is descriptive method. The number of research samples are 100 respondents. All data was collected through a questionnaire. Test the research hypothesis using multiple regression analysis. Next, a Simultaneous Test (Test F) is performed to determine the significant effect of all independent variables on the dependent variable. Testing is done by comparing the value of F_{count} with F_{table} at an error rate of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$). To find out the percentage contribution of the influence of the independent variables simultaneously on the dependent variable, the coefficient of determination (R^2) is used. The results showed that the organizational structure, employee capabilities and service systems significantly influence the performance of SSOA services in Ternate.

KEYWORDS -Insurance, Service system, Social Security

I. INTRODUCTION

Globalization has caused Indonesia to be flooded with many world-class insurance companies that provide the best services for workers in Indonesia. The existence of foreign companies is a major challenge for national insurance companies, especially state-owned companies that are responsible for providing services to all levels of workers in Indonesia. Especially now that public demands for effective, efficient and satisfying public services are increasing.

Communities as service subjects no longer like convoluted, long-standing and risky services because of the long bureaucratic chain. The public wants the freshness of service that can understand the needs and desires that are fulfilled in a relatively short time. This desire needs to be addressed and fulfilled by companies engaged in services, to maintain their image.

Many factors affect the quality of public sector services. Research by Bawole, et al (2015) shows that factors affecting the quality of public services include organizational structure, employee capabilities and service systems. The organizational structure is related to the composition of tasks and responsibilities that show work procedures. The ability of employees related to the nature or responsibilities held by employees in work. Whereas the service system deals with a whole series of interrelated and influential units in providing services to the public.

This research was conducted to determine the factors that have an impact on the quality of public services at the Office of the Social Security Organizing Agency (SSOA) of Ternate City. SSOA is a public legal

entity that provides protection for workers to overcome certain socio-economic risks and their implementation uses social insurance mechanisms. As a State Institution engaged in the field of social insurance, SSOA is entrusted with organizing a workforce social security program, which includes Work Accident Insurance, Death Insurance, Old Age Insurance and Pension Insurance.

On one hand SSOA Ternate City has high potential for membership in conducting service activities as well as submitting claims for the guarantee program. This condition can be seen from the transaction conditions every day. Where the service office is never empty in carrying out administrative activities. However, from observations made there are still problems that often occur, namely related to employee performance in providing services to the community, so that it affects the satisfaction of SSOA participants. This condition can be seen from the percentage of public service performance satisfaction performed by SSOA Ternate in 2014 to 2017, which can be detailed in the following table:

Table 1. Data on Public Service Satisfaction Performance from 2014 to 2017 at SSOA in Ternate City

Year	Public Service Performance Satisfaction Targets (%)	Realization (%)
2014	70	69
2015	75	72
2016	80	75
2017	85	74

Source: SSOA of Ternate city, 2018

Table 1.1, the percentage of satisfaction data on the performance of public services, from 2014 to 2017 which shows that the performance of services performed by the Social Security Organizing Agency (SSOA) for the last 4 years (2014 to 2017) has not been able to provide satisfaction for SSOA participants. Participant's satisfaction or dissatisfaction is the participant's response to the evaluation and the actual performance felt after its use which is also related to the quality of the service provider. Customers or consumers will be satisfied with the service if the performance of the product or service meets their expectations, whereas if the performance of the product or service exceeds consumer expectations, consumers will be very satisfied or happy, but if the performance is below consumer expectations, consumers are not satisfied.

It is said not to give satisfaction because the services provided are not as expected by SSOA customers. This can be seen from the results of observations and interviews with SSOA customers at the Office of the Social Security Organizing Agency (SSOA) in Ternate, where there are still complaints that are felt by the community regarding the quality of services provided. This can be seen from the lack of employee speed in providing services, uncomfortable waiting rooms, due to lack of air conditioning and unorganized spatial planning so that it affects the services provided, in addition to the lack of friendliness and professionalism of employees in serving the community and disbursement from the existence claims by the community or customers of SSOA that seem long and convoluted so that this affects the dissatisfaction of SSOA customers in Ternate.

Based on the problems that have been stated above, the authors are interested in conducting research on the Determinants of Public Service Performance in the Manpower Social Security Organizing Agency (SSOA) in Ternate City.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A basic understanding of performance is the results achieved from certain work functions or activities over a certain period of time. Whereas performance measurement is as a method to assess the progress that has been achieved compared to the objectives set. Based on the above understanding, it can be said that basically performance is the result of achievement or work achievement obtained by an organization in order to achieve

the goals and objectives that have been determined and agreed upon within a certain time period. While performance measurement is a tool or method used to provide an assessment of how much the level of work performance or achievement of goals and targets that have been determined (Gomes, 2013).

Public services are closely related to the government, because one of the responsibilities of the government is to provide services to the public. The quality of public services received directly by the public can be used as a benchmark in assessing the quality of government. Public services in its development arise from the existence of obligations as a process of carrying out government activities both individually and in groups (Sugiandi, 2011).

According to Law Number 25 Year 2009 of the Republic of Indonesia concerning Public Services, it is stated that public services are activities or service needs for every citizen and population of goods, services, and or administrative services provided by public service providers. The scope of public services can be classified into two forms, namely:

- 1) Public Goods and Services Service's. Procurement and distribution of public goods and services can be said to dominate all services provided by the government to the public. This category of public service can be carried out by a government institution which partly or wholly funds are state assets that cannot be separated or can be carried out by government-owned companies which partly or wholly funds come from separate state assets (State-Owned Enterprises).
- 2) Administrative Services. Public services in this category include administrative actions required by the state and regulated by law to realize personal, family, honour and property protection as well as administrative activities carried out by non-governmental institutions required by the state and regulated in legislation and applicable based on agreements with service recipients.

Based on the provisions of the law above, public services are the spearhead of interaction between the community and the government. Where, the performance of the bureaucracy can be assessed one of them by looking at the extent of the quality of public services (Arif, 2010).

1.Public Service Performance

Performance is work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization, in an effort to achieve goals legally, not breaking the law and in accordance with morals and ethics. There are three concepts that can be used as indicators of government organizational performance, namely, responsiveness of responsibility and accountability (Sedarmayanti, 2016).

Meanwhile, according to Pasolong (2013), there are five basics that can be used as indicators of performance of public services, including:

- 1) Service, which shows how many services are provided.
- 2) Economy, which shows whether the costs used are cheaper than planned.
- 3) Efficient, which shows the comparison of results achieved with expenditure.
- 4) Effectiveness, which shows the comparison of expected results with the results achieved.
- 5) Equity, which shows the level of potential fairness of the resulting policy.

From the explanation above it can be concluded that performance indicators are a means or tool to measure the results of an activity or assess organizational performance. According to Dwiyanto (2012) states indicators to measure the performance of public services include:

- 1) Productivity.

Productivity not only measures efficiency, but also service effectiveness. Productivity is generally understood as the ratio between input and output. The concept of productivity is felt to be narrowly crossed and then tries to develop a broader measure of productivity by including how much public service has expected results as one of the important performance indicators. Productivity indicators are widely used to measure and find out the output produced by an organization at a certain time period.

2) Service quality

Service quality issues tend to become increasingly important in explaining the performance of public service organizations. Many negative views are formed about organizations arising from public dissatisfaction with the quality of services received from educational institutions, youth and sports services.

3) Responsiveness

Responsiveness is the ability of organizations to recognize community needs, set agendas and priorities for services, and develop public service programs in accordance with community needs and aspirations. Responsiveness is included in one of the performance indicators because responsiveness directly reflects the ability of educational institutions, youth and sports in carrying out its mission and objectives, especially to meet the needs of the community.

4) Responsibility

Responsibility explains whether the implementation of education office activities, youth and sports services is carried out in accordance with the correct administrative principles or in accordance with organizational policies, both explicit and implicit. Therefore, one day responsibilities can clash with responsiveness.

5) Accountability

Accountability is related to how much the policies and activities of education, youth and sports services are subject to political officials elected by the people. The assumption is that political officials because they are elected by the people will automatically represent the interests of the people. Performance must be assessed by external measures, such as values and norms that apply in society. An activity of the education office, youth and sports institutions has high accountability if the activity is considered true and in accordance with the norms that develop in the community.

2. Influence of Organizational Structure on Public Service Performance

The dominant organizational structure is determined by strategy, organizational size, technology, environment and power control. Robbins (2015) revealed that a clear understanding of work procedures and system in service can be understood when employees have adequate knowledge in accordance with their field of work. This must be followed by placing employees in the right fields and places.

A clear organizational structure will certainly be able to distribute the tasks of each part in the organization to be clear. According to Moenir (2010), organizing service functions, in terms of structure and mechanism, is very instrumental in ensuring the quality and smoothness of public services.

Work mechanisms in organizations that strongly support service performance (Moenir, 2010), including:

- 1) The systems, is the arrangement of components that affect and are interconnected. Similar to the human body system, if one system and sub-system is disrupted then the other system will also be disrupted. Likewise with the service system.
- 2) The Procedure, can be translated as a mechanism that applies in an organization and has certain restrictions. Because the procedure regulates the good deeds entering and leaving the organization, it must be known and understood by the person concerned, both employees and parties outside the organization.

- 3) The method, is how one completes the stages of a series of work, is easy to do and efficient among several existing methods. In office organizations there are methods for typing letters, handling incoming mail, handling outgoing mail, filing, bookkeeping, and others.

3. Influence of Work Ability on Public Service Performance

According to Nawawi (2015), the leaders' interest in the ability of workers is centered on the ability of employees. This view of work relations with employees related to their nature can be summarized in the statement "A happy worker is a productive worker" much is done by leaders in making their workers successful in their work.

The results of research conducted by Shafiah (2014), can be seen that there is an influence between the ability of employees to work on service performance. This influence shows that if there is a change or increase in the ability of employees, their performance will improve. The results of the analysis prove that the achievement of employee performance can be reflected in the company's efforts to motivate employees so that they can work optimally. This is also supported by the ability of employees to work, in this case regarding the knowledge, skills and attitudes of employees.

4. Influence of Service Systems on Public Service Performance

Service system is the overall unity of a service that is interrelated, if there is a service system that is disrupted then overall it will disrupt the service itself. The service system will provide service procedures that have standards and can provide control mechanisms in the service system so that all forms of irregularities or errors will be easily identified (Dwiyanto, 2012).

In the aspect of implementation, the employee in charge of providing services to the community is the spearhead in achieving good quality public services. So that public services can be said to be good, then the main role is how the workings, attitudes and behavior of these employees in providing services to the public or users of public services.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a confirmation study that aims to test the hypothesis. Because the theoretical basis used has been formed, so it is only retested whether the theory can be justified. The results of the study are explained quantitatively in the form of numbers accompanied by explanations (Sugiyono, 2016). In this study the variables tested were the influence of organizational structure (X1), employee ability (X2) and service system (X3) on Public Service Performance (Y).

The population in this study were Social Security Organizing Agency (SSOA) participants in Ternate as many as 22,363 respondents. Given the large number, then to determine the number of samples used by Slovin theory proposed by Sujarweni (2016) using the formula $n = N / (1 + (N \times e^2))$. Where n = sample size, N = population and e = standard error. From this calculation the result of the number of samples is 99.55 or rounded up to 100 respondents.

All research data were collected through a questionnaire that was distributed to all respondents. The research hypothesis test uses multiple regression analysis to find out each independent variable (X) to the dependent variable (Y) (Sugiyono, 2010). Next, a Simultaneous Test (Test F) is performed to determine the significant effect of all independent variables on the dependent variable. Testing is done by comparing the value of F count with F table at an error rate of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$). To find out the percentage contribution of the influence of the independent variables simultaneously on the dependent variable, the coefficient of determination (R²) test is used.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Analysis of Multiple Linear Regression Equations

Analysis was carried out based on the unstandardized coefficient value of the regression results between the organizational structure, employee capabilities, and service systems on the performance of public services in Social Security Organizing Agency (SSOA) of Ternate city which was processed using computerized data processed using SPSS version 24.

Table 2. Output Regression Coefficient

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.382	.396		.965	.337
Organizational structure	.380	.097	.311	3.907	.000
Employee ability	.275	.109	.259	2.535	.013
Service system	.278	.095	.298	2.925	.004

Source: Primary data, 2019

From the table above, the regression equation obtained is $Y = 0.382 + 0.380X_1 + 0.275X_2 + 0.278X_3$, so that an explanation can be given as follows:

- 1) b_0 (constant) = 0.382, which means that without the organizational structure, employee capabilities, and service systems, the performance of public services in BPJS Ternate City is 0.382%.
- 2) Regression coefficient $b_1 = 0.380$ which means that the organizational structure has a positive influence on the performance of public services in SSOA Ternate, if the organizational structure is good, the performance of public services will increase by 0.380%.
- 3) Regression coefficient $b_2 = 0.275$ which means that the ability of employees has a positive influence on the performance of public services in SSOA Ternate, if the organizational structure is good then the performance of public services will increase by 0.275%.
- 4) Regression coefficient $b_3 = 0.278$ which means that the service system has a positive influence on the performance of public services in SSOA Ternate, if the service system is good, the performance of public services will increase by 0.278%.

2. Correlation Coefficient Analysis and Determination

Table 3. Adjusted R Square

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.690 ^a	.476	.460	.55958

a. Predictors: (Constant), Service system, Organizational structure, Employee ability

b. Dependent Variable: performance of public services

Source: Primary data, 2019

From the calculation of the correlation coefficient, the value of $R = 0.690$ (a positive R value and close to 1) shows that the three independent variables, namely organizational structure, employee ability, and service system, have a strong relationship with public service performance at SSOA Ternate. Adjusted R square value of 0.460, indicates that the percentage of influence of independent variables (organizational structure, employee ability, and service system) is able to explain 46% of the variation in the performance variables of public services in SSOA Ternate. While the remaining 54% is influenced by other variables not included in this study.

3. Hypothesis test

Hypothesis testing proposed in this study will be carried out from the results of partial tests using the t-test. While for the proof of the intervening test is based on the concurrent influence of the variables studied, using the f-test.

Table 4. Partial Testing Results (t test)

Model	Sig
Organizational structure	0,000
Employee ability	0,013
Service system	0,004

Source: Primary data, 2019

Based on the results of the partial test (t test) in table 4, an explanation can be given as follows:

- 1) The effect of organizational structure on the performance of public services by comparing the probability value with the standard value, where the results of the processed data obtained a probability value of 0,000 <0.05, it can be concluded that the organizational structure has a significant influence on the performance of public services at the Social Security Organizing Agency (SSOA) Ternate.
- 2) The effect of the ability of employees on the performance of public services by comparing the probability value with the standard value, where the results of the processed data obtained a probability value of 0.013 <0.05, it can be concluded that the ability of employees has a significant influence on the performance of public services in the Social Security Organizing Agency (SSOA) Ternate.
- 3) The effect of the service system on the performance of public services by comparing the probability value with the standard value, where the processed data obtained a probability value of 0.004 <0.05, it can be concluded that the service system has a significant influence on the performance of public services in the Social Security Organizing Agency (SSOA) Ternate.

Table 5. Concurrent Testing Results (F test)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	27.299	3	9.100	29.060	.000 ^b
Residual	30.061	96	.313		
Total	57.360	99			

a. Dependent Variable: performance of public services

Source: Primary data, 2019

From the results of simultaneous testing (F test) in table 5, the probability value is 0,000 <0.05. Then it can be concluded that the organizational structure, employee capabilities, and service systems have a simultaneous influence on the performance of public services in SSOA Ternate.

V. DISCUSSION

1. Influence of Organizational Structure on Public Service Performance

Based on the results of the study, the regression value obtained for the organizational structure of 0.380, this means that the organizational structure has a positive influence on the performance of public services in SSOA Ternate. Then from the results of the regression test, the probability value for competence is 0,000. This can be interpreted that the organizational structure has a significant influence on the performance of public services in SSOA Ternate. This is consistent with the theory put forward by Robbins (2015) that organizational structure has three components, namely: complexity, formalization and centralization. Complexity means in the organizational structure considering the level of differentiation that exists in the organization including the level of specialization or division of labor, the number of levels in the organization and the extent to which

organizational units are geographically dispersed. Formalization means that in the organizational structure contains procedures or procedures for how an activity is carried out (standard operating procedures).

2. Influence of Work Ability on Public Service Performance

From the results of the study obtained a regression value for the ability of employees of 0.275, this means that the ability of employees has a positive influence on the performance of public services at SSOA Ternate. Then from the regression test results, the probability value for the employee's ability is 0.013. This can be interpreted that the ability of employees has a significant influence on the performance of public services in the SSOA of Ternate. This is consistent with the theory put forward by Nawawi (2015) suggesting that the interests of leaders towards the work ability of an employee tend to be centered on employee performance. This view is about the relationship between employee work abilities and performance.

The results of the questionnaire were obtained empirical findings related to the responses of respondents regarding the ability of employees that affect the quality of public services, obtained findings that employees are able to respond to all participant complaints, the ability of employees to collaborate with other fellow employees, speed, friendliness of employees in serving SSOA customers and SSOA employee treatment every customer is not discriminatory or discriminated against.

3. Influence of Service Systems on Public Service Performance

Based on the results of the study obtained a regression value for the service system of 0.278, this means that the service system has a positive influence on the performance of public services in SSOA of Ternate. Then from the regression test results, the probability value for the service system is 0.004. This can be interpreted that the service system has a significant influence on the performance of public services in the SSOA of Ternate. This is consistent with the theory put forward by Zemke and Albrecht (1985) that the quality of public services is the result of interaction from various aspects, namely one of the service systems.

From the results of the distribution of the questionnaire obtained findings related to the service system regarding the convenience of SSOA customers in obtaining services, clarity of information provided by employees, Protection of the impact of the results of services provided by employees, Practicality and convenience of the community or SSOA Customers in obtaining services from employees and the terms and costs clear and detailed administration.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research that has been done, some conclusions can be drawn from the results of the analysis as follows:

- 1) The organizational structure, employee capabilities and service system significantly influence on the performance of public services in the Social Security Organizing Agency (SSOA) in Ternate City.
- 2) From the results of regression testing, it can be concluded that the dominant factor affecting the performance of public services in the Social Security Organizing Agency (SSOA) in Ternate City is the organizational structure.

VII. CONCLUSION

Suggestions that can be given in connection with the results of this study are as follows:

- 1) The need for a good organizational structure so that the activities in each unit at SSOA in Ternate are directed. Because until now there are still several positions in the company's nomenclature that have not been filled, causing the service process to be slow.
- 2) To further improve the performance of public services, it is necessary to further improve the ability, speed and agility of employees in serving labour insurance participants, one of which is providing excellent service training on an ongoing basis to SSOA and outsourcing employees such as Security and Cleaning Services.

- 3) Also recommended to improve the performance of public services, SSOA Ternate needs to innovate in accordance with the development of the electronic digital era by further maximizing E-service channels, such as E-claim, online queues, E-PLKK, and others.

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